

wasteless

Waste Quantification Solutions to Limit Environmental Stress

Lead Partner: Hungarian Hospitality Employers' Association
Month: M3 – March 2023

D7.7 – Website and social media

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V0.1	02/03/2023	Lajos Böröcz	Initial draft	draft
V0.2	14/03/2023	WP7 partners	Contribution to all Sections	draft
V0.3	21/03/2023	Lajos Böröcz	Second draft	draft
V0.4	23/03/2023	IFA	Peer review	draft
V0.5	31/03/2023	UTAD	Peer review	draft
V1.0	31/03/2023	UTAD	Final approval and submission to the E.C	Final

Executive Summary

This Deliverable - Website and social media - (D7.7) is part of the work carried out under Work Package 7 (WP7) Exploitation, communication, dissemination, and food system actor engagement and relates to the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan (D7.2 due M6).

This deliverable is the documentation of the project website and the social media accounts created by WP7 at M3 of the project. Through the development of the project, the website and SoMe accounts will be updated accordingly. The website and the SoMe accounts will provide the necessary virtual environment for the project to achieve in part the communication objectives.

WASTELESS will use the [website](#) as its main platform to show the achievements and goals of the project as well as its case studies and best practices, to link the Knowledge Sharing Platform and to host the WASTELESS Community including tools, trainings and a blog. WASTELESS will also use the social media (SoMe) accounts, [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#) to increase engagement and the number of people reached and be able to share its main outcomes as widely as possible.

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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
CD	Communication and Dissemination
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
EU	European Union
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
FW	Food Waste
FWM	Food Waste Monitoring
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KSP	Knowledge Sharing Platform
PR	Public Relations
SoMe	Social media
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The WASTELESS project (2023-2025) aims to develop tools and recommendations for measuring and monitoring food loss and waste (FLW), which will ultimately contribute to its reduction by at least 20% annually. Additionally, WASTELESS will carry research activities on innovative processes and streams to valorise unavoidable FLW.

To expand WASTELESS impact a Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan will be used to promote the project and its results (communication), to make the results public (dissemination) and to make concrete use of the results achieved (exploitation). The communication activities will target citizens and stakeholders and as such the content will be adapted so that everyone can understand the stakes and goals of the project without having to understand all the technical and scientific details. Two of the major means of communication will be: the project website and the social media (SoMe) accounts.

The project website is a virtual place where various communication campaigns will take place, to reach a much wider group than the specific target groups. The SoMe accounts LinkedIn, Twitter and Research Gate were selected in agreement with the coordinator and the WP7 involved partners. LinkedIn is used by most of the people from the business world, Twitter mainly lets their users uncover new content and trending news in their area of interest and Research Gate is used by a large community of researchers. However, Research Gate has announced in February 2023 that projects will be discontinued from 31st March 2023, and thus despite mentioned in the grant agreement and selected by the coordinator and partners involved in WP7 it will not be possible to be used. Facebook was also mentioned in the grant agreement but was unanimously voted by the coordinator and partners involved in WP7 not to be used since in the latest years it focuses on making connections with family, friends, and people.

Content creation for both website and SoMe will be a team effort where all the partners are welcomed and in charge of creating the necessary amounts of inputs for the website. The WASTELESS communication and content manager (VIMOSZ) maintains the contacts, checks, edits, and places the articles and, where necessary, provides the author with feedback and writes articles as well. To keep the record and a steady, organised flow of contents a DEC Reporting document and an internal publication calendar will be used. VIMOSZ will also check if all the contents are being uploaded in the DEC Reporting document and if necessary, notifies the partners involved.

The target audience is defined in detail in the DEC Plan. Involving all stakeholders, the aim is to communicate life-changing results, to help consumers understand the importance of food waste prevention and how to reduce it and measure the waste. Several target audiences have been specified from policymakers through investors to civil society. The desired reach of each target audience can be found in Annex I.

In the following sections the website and the SoMe accounts will be described in detail.

2. Project Website

The project [Website](#) (domain wastelesseu.com.) was developed by VIMOSZ and was officially launched in March 2023. It will enhance visibility and communication about the project by including information about the project itself, the partners of the consortium, project results (including the developed tools and methods, conceptual, guidelines, etc.), news and upcoming events, case studies, blog post in connection with FLW, other related links and information and more. Other resources will be identified and created as necessary and distributed through beneficiaries according to the project development.

The website has many different subpages and functions to satisfy all the needs the project requires. Here interested people can find all the information related to the project. This will create a strong online presence for WASTELESS, will contribute to a low carbon footprint by avoiding unnecessary printed versions of the publications and will follow the sustainability standards of the present.

The design of the website follows the concept of the Brandbook so that it is coherent with the project's visual identity. VIMOSZ is responsible for applying and making sure these visual elements are used in every situation.

Accessibility features are built in so that everybody can engage with the project and with the contents in the site. These accessibility features include button to increase font size, button to change the text background contrast, skip links for users to navigate to the main content of the page, ARIA marker roles for improved navigation for screen reader users.

The website structure consists of the following pages and subpages: Home, About, Partners, Outcomes (Tools, Case studies, Publications), Community (Blog, Trainings, Newsroom), Knowledge Sharing Platform, Contact. On all pages the following are included: Twitter feed, EU funding acknowledgment, copyrights as well as different tabs to access other information.

The website will be maintained for at least three years after the project ends to ensure its sustainability and VIMOSZ will be the responsible partner.

2.1. Home

By scrolling down on the 'Home' page one can go through all the important information in connection with the project (Figure 1). In every subsection of the 'Home' page there is a dedicated button that takes them to the appropriate page/subpage where more information can be found.

2.2 About

In this page guests can read about the project in details: short description, objectives, project details and an additionally information about Food Losses and Waste can be found below in the page (Figure2).

2.3 Partners

Here all the partners are gathered with useful information in connection with their role in the project, as well as their field of work. The multidisciplinary consortium comprises 16 beneficiaries, 12 affiliated entities and 1 associated partner (Figure 3). Each partner has its logo that is linked to a page where the partner's name, short (300 characters max.) introduction and role on the project is displayed.

Figure 1. Home page (Landing) of WASTELESS website.

Home About Partners Outcomes Community Knowledge Sharing Platform Contact

About

Waste Quantification Solutions to Limit Environmental Stress

WASTELESS (2023-2025) aims to develop tools and recommendations for measuring and monitoring food losses and waste (FLW) which will ultimately contribute to its reduction by at least 20% annually. The main objective of the project is to develop tools to measure FLW in critical and less-known food supply chains and propose ways of quantifying the data. At the same time, it will develop an innovative set of decision-support tools for all those working along the food chain across the EU, to enable reduction and re-use of food waste in the long term. WASTELESS will carry out five case studies to understand utilisation and role/contribution of specific food groups such as fruits and vegetables, fruit juices, processed meat, dairy products and cereals in the FLW.

Objectives

- ✓ Develop and test a mix of innovative tools and methodologies for Food Loss and Waste (FLW) measurement and monitoring, generating robust FLW data on critical and poorly understood Food Supply Chains (FSC)
- ✓ Recommend a harmonised methodological Framework for FLW quantification
- ✓ Develop a decision support systemic Toolbox targeting all food value chain stakeholders enabling the duplication of WASTELESS collection points across EU territories and different food commodities.

Project Details

- **Project number:** 101084222
- **Project duration:** 3 years. Starting date: 1 January 2023. End date: 31 December 2025.
- **Project Coordinator:** Universidade De Tras-Os-Montes E Alto Douro (UTAD)
- **Participants:** 17 organisations from 12 countries
- **Total budget:** 5 458 233 EUR
- **Target groups:** food service stakeholders, food industries, retail, households, selected supply chains

About Food Waste

While hunger is one of the world's most important health risks, approximately one third of food produced at the global level (1.3bn tonnes) is wasted every year. Individuals in developed countries waste as much food (222 million tons) as all food production in sub-Saharan Africa (203 million tons).

About 88 million tonnes of food are wasted annually in the EU, at an estimated cost of €143 billion with tremendous negative impacts on society, the environment, and the economy.

Figure 2. About page of WASTELESS website.

Figure 3. Partners page of WASTELESS website.

2.4 Outcomes

This page aims to present the results of the project and is divided in three subpages: tools, case studies, and publications (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Outcomes page of WASTELESS website.

The Tools subpage will detail the specific tools developed in the project such as ‘Measuring and Monitoring tools’, ‘Decision Support Toolbox’ and ‘Data Collection Hub’. The tools and their description and use will be added once available. ‘Measuring and Monitoring tools’ it will include the (1) electronic registry supported by a blockchain system, (2) the computer vision-based image analysis, (3) the AI-based data driven approach for FWM in retailer and consumers, (4) the surplus measurement and management tool and (5) the automatic system for FW assessment at households.

Figure 5. Tools subpage of outcomes page of WASTELESS website.

Case studies subpage will give information on the six case studies as described in the grant agreement. These case studies will occur in 8 territories (France, Spain, Hungary, Italy, Estonia, Slovenia, Portugal, and Turkey) and with Primary producers, Agri-Food Industrials, Food retailers, Food services and Consumers. Case studies for FLW measuring and monitoring in (1) food industries, (2) food retailers, (3) food services, (4) households and (5) selected supply chains.

The six case studies will be described in detail and updates on their development will be posted regularly.

Publications subpage will list all the scientific publications and any type of article published in peer-reviewed journals and other magazines in print and online; abstracts and presentations (oral or poster) given at conferences, symposia, or meetings at local, regional, national, and international events; technical reports; book chapters; doctoral, master and bachelor theses; patents; deliverables (when public). If no link available a PDF file will be provided.

2.5 Community

This page hosts the WASTELESS Community of Practice, and it includes three subpages: training, blog, and newsroom (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Community page of WASTELESS website.

The training section will include links to all trainings which will be developed during the project on different topics: e.g. ways to measure FLW, how to reduce FLW for retailers, consumers, demonstration of measurement tools developed in WASTELESS, etc.

The Blog will be the interactive part of the website. It will be user-generated and like a knowledge hub with high-quality articles full of expertise on specific topics related to the project. VIMOSZ will manage the blog and its content. Partners and communication managers of the partners will be stimulated to engage and participate actively in creating content on alternative moments. Each partner must submit at least 4 articles a year. For the WASTELESS blog articles, we aim for quality rather than quantity. The WASTELESS blog will also include news from all over the world referring to: explanation of a new phenomenon, trends and developments, strategies, and others related to the FLW and overall food & beverage sector. The articles will be encouraged to be about best practices, advice, and knowledge about FLW and all its aspects.

The newsroom subpage will include press releases, the WASTELESS newsletters and any future related events. In addition, there is part in this subpage where people can subscribe to the newsletter. VIMOSZ is responsible for creating these publications.

2.6 Knowledge Sharing Platform

By clicking on the ‘Knowledge Sharing Platform’ button the guest will be redirected to the [SFS Innovation Platform](#) website (Figure 7), a collaborative platform where people can find innovations, initiatives, publications and weblinks related to sustainable foods and to the projects that are platform contributors. WASTELESS will use this platform as an online environment to share knowledge on food systems and raise awareness about the project among different stakeholders. WASTELESS (through IFA) will manage (Figure 8) the [SFS Innovation Platform](#). The platform will be described in detail in Deliverable 7.1 - Knowledge sharing platforms for food systems (Due M18).

Figure 7. Home page (Landing) of the KSP.

2.7 Contact

There is an email address A message can be sent from the website to the email address created (info@wastelesseu.com) to which people can write letters, share opinions, and primarily engage with the project. VIMOSZ is responsible for managing the emails received and depending on the topic contacting the responsible consortium member.

The screenshot shows the 'Managers' subpage of the Sustainable Food System Innovation Platform website. The page features a search bar, a language selection dropdown, and a navigation menu with links for HOME, ABOUT US, INVENTORIES, NETWORKING, TRAINING, and REGISTER/LOGIN. The main content area is titled 'Managers' and includes an introductory paragraph about collaboration in H2020 projects CO-FRESH and FAIRCHAIN. Below this, there are four project logos with descriptions: FAIRCHAIN, CO-FRESH, EU4Advice, and wasteless.

Select Language

Search...

SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEM
INNOVATION PLATFORM

HOME ABOUT US INVENTORIES NETWORKING TRAINING REGISTER/LOGIN

HOME > ABOUT US
Managers

Collaboration is a key to success and two H2020 projects CO-FRESH and FAIRCHAIN put collaboration into action. These projects increase the competitiveness and sustainability of agri-food value chains through innovations, new approaches, and knowledge sharing. Together, they maintain and grow this Innovation Platform by

- Sharing project information on food supply chain innovations;
- Publicizing through thePlatform Initiative Inventory;
- Generating training materials on best practices in food supply chain;
- And ultimately engaging more and more stakeholders in innovative food supply chains.

 The **FAIRCHAIN Project** develops intermediate food value chains in fruit & vegetable and dairy sectors. These combine elements from short and long value chains for food systems that are more sustainable environmentally, socially, and economically. The focus is on postharvest, where there are processing and retail power imbalances in conventional supply chains.

 The **CO-FRESH Project** aims to provide techniques, tools and insights on how to make agri-food value chains more environmentally sustainable, socio-economically balanced and economically competitive. The project pilots several agri-food value chain innovations to see how they, in combination, can improve environmental and socio-economic sustainability.

 The **EU4ADVICE Project** will promote sustainable short food supply chain (SFSC) models. These should empower producers and consumers, reduce the environmental footprint of food systems, and enhance the competitiveness of the agri-food system. Identifying and connecting SFSC advisers will boost their role as catalysers of knowledge flow from research to practice. Ultimately, effective integration into national AKIS will result.

 The **WASTELESS Project** (2023-2025) aims to develop and test a mix of innovative tools and methodologies for food losses and waste (FLW) measurement and monitoring. Additionally, it will also carry research activities on innovative processes and streams to valorise unavoidable FLW. WASTELESS ambition is to promote the reduction of FLW by at least 20% annually.

Figure 8. About us subpage of the KSP.

3. Social media accounts

VIMOSZ has created the SoMe accounts of the project to: communicate to a wider and diverse audience than the predefined target groups; to raise the profile of the project; to publicise project developments; to engage in dialogue; to build relationships with others in the field, and to monitor what is being said about WASTELESS and related issues. The project uses 2 SoMe platforms: Twitter and LinkedIn. Both platforms have different groups as their main users.

All WASTELESS posts on SoMe will contain the hashtag #WASTELESS. Further, other hashtags relevant for the project will be used: e.g., #FLW, #foodwaste #foodloss, #H2020, #EUFarm2Fork. A common hashtag with the sister project (FOLOU) will be decided until M6 and used collaboratively.

The predefined target groups can be found in the Annex I.

3.1 Twitter

Twitter is a very efficient online social media and social networking service on which users send and respond publicly or privately texts, images and videos and could reach as many as 300 million users. Here WASTELESS is represented as a community, creating engagement with stakeholders as a priority (Figure 9). The mission is sharing continuously knowledge and content straight from the website on relevant topics for the broader public.

Figure 9. WASTELESS Twitter page.

3.2 LinkedIn

[LinkedIn](#) is the most trusted network and business community for professionals and also a publishing platform. As a business -focused social media platform had as of January 2023 900+ million registered members. The posts here will be mainly about sharing relevant information of the consortium, the project, major outcomes and its partners for the stakeholders including businesses and other institutes. Also, option to discuss knowledge and get feedback and support with other experts on the relevant WASTELESS topics to gather relevant information (Figure 10).

Figure 10. WASTELESS LinkedIn page.

3.3 Content creation

Posting on the SoMe will be done regularly. Content to be published on social media includes but is not limited to project press releases; announcements of progress; reports on conferences and meetings, news of milestone achievements, information about forthcoming events; news on research and developments on related issues from all over the world. An internal [SoMe document](#) (Annex II) was created to manage the SoMe posts. Here partners can provide their input for SoMe posts.

EuroFIR will manage the SoMe accounts and will do the posting using HootSuite tool. A redaction team was formed and will meet monthly to decide on the content of posts, campaigns, etc. The redaction team includes different partners: EuroFIR (Angelika Mantur-Vierendeel, am@eurofir.org), VIMOSZ (Lajos Böröcz, hha@vimosz.org), EUROPATAT (Berta Redondo, berta.redondo@europatat.eu) and IFA (Sofia Reis, sofia.reis@iseki-food.net).

4. Monitoring and evaluation

A DEC Reporting document was created and will be used by all partners to list all activities related to dissemination, exploitation and communication, including the communication activities published on the WASTELESS website and SoMe accounts. VIMOSZ will oversee the reporting on communication activities by the partners in due course.

The evaluation procedure of the website and SoMe performance is part of the DEC Plan where the key performance indicators (KPI) have been formulated. The success of the website and SoMe will be evaluated yearly by analysing the analytics of the website and SoMe accounts and comparison with the KPIs (Annex III). These will enable the WP7 partners to manage possible deviations and make any needed updates in a timely manner.

5. Conclusion

The major outputs of this deliverable are the project website and SoMe accounts. These platforms were created in M3 of the project and will be used and updated to match the WASTELESS objectives and requirements. With their use the project has created a brand and virtual ecosystem which can outlive the duration of WASTELESS project and be a very valuable tool including useful information in the challenge to reduce FLW.

Annex I – Table of Target audience

WHO	Desired range
European, national, and regional policymakers and food agencies	30
Civil Society	50
European, national and regional private sector	300
Scientific community working on measuring, monitoring and reducing FLW	30
General public and other relevant stakeholders and actors of the food supply chain	3000
Other research projects and initiatives	20
Project partners and their network of contacts	100.000

Annex II – SoMe internal document

AT:C1 Ideas and management for SoMe posts - Wasteless accounts

	A	B	C	D
1	Ideas and management for SoMe posts - Wasteless accounts			
2	Recommended timing	Topic	Source	Post content
3	28 February	Press release kick of meeting	Common PR	
4	March	Partner's presentations	Partners	
5	March	European Citizens' panel provides recommendations on tackling food waste	https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/sante/items/777967/en	
6	22 March	WASTELESS project presentation (roll up) on the Dare2Change event	UTAD	
7				
8				
9	31 March	Launch of the website	https://wastelesseu.com/	
10				
11	8 July	WASTELESS project presentation on the 7th International ISEKI conference	IFA	
12				
13	29 September	International Day of Awareness of Food Loss and Waste (IDAFW)	FAO	
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25				

Annex III – Table of Key Performance Indicators

Name of the KPI	Target at M36	Type of data
Twitter		
Number of posts	150	HootSuite Analytics
Number of followers	400	
Post key interactions	1500	
Post traffic	1500	
LinkedIn		
Number of posts	150	HootSuite Analytics
Number of followers	400	
Page engagement	1500	
Page clicks	1500	
Website		
Number of visits	2500	Google Analytics
Number of pages/visit	3	
Average time spent/visit (min)	2	

